

The need for rigour: A rejoinder to Brand et al. (2023)

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The need for rigour: A rejoinder to Brand et al. (2023)

Significance

This article critically examines the legal inaccuracies in Brand et al.'s work on data protection laws in various African countries. Key points include:

- Emphasis on the necessity of primary sources for rigour in legal research.
- Identification of misinterpretations in Brand et al.'s analysis of data protection legislation in Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria, and South Africa.
- Clarification of the law and corrections to Brand et al.'s assertions.
- Critique of Brand et al.'s reliance on a secondary, non-peer-reviewed source.
- Recommendation for the retraction of Brand et al.'s original article and rebuttal due to multiple inaccuracies and lack of rigour.

Introduction

Legal academic debate is important, as it deepens our collective understanding of the law. The existence of legal academic debate (and lawsuits about points of law, not fact) demonstrate that lawyers may *reasonably* differ about the interpretation of the law and how it should be applied in specific circumstances. Society's understanding of the law can only progress if lawyers are willing to think creatively and consider novel—and even provocative—interpretations of the law. A good example in the context of South African data protection law is the recent debate on whether the *Protection of Personal Information Act* 4 of 2013 (POPIA) applies to health research.^{1,2,3} These kinds of debates should be encouraged.

However, not any interpretation of the law is necessarily a reasonable and well-argued interpretation thereof. In order to make a positive contribution to legal knowledge, it is essential that legal research must adhere to well-established standards of *rigour*. While some elements of rigour are common amongst all fields of research, such as logic and the need to substantiate one's conclusions with reasons, rigour in legal research places great emphasis on *authority*. This entails that any analysis of the law must first and foremost be based on primary sources of the law, such as acts of parliament, subsidiary legislation, and case law. While peer-reviewed articles can be valuable sources to enrich understanding, they should supplement, but not substitute reliance on the relevant primary source. Non-peer-reviewed texts about the law should be handled with circumspection. Relying on the primary source itself, rather than other's interpretations thereof, facilitates both accuracy and comprehensiveness. These standards are foundational to rigour in legal research.

¹ Bronstein V, Nyachowe DT. Streamlining regulatory processes for health researchers: To what extent does POPIA apply? *S Afr Med J* 2023;113(8):1319-1321. <https://doi.org/10.7196/SAMJ.2023.v113i8.781>

² Thaldar D. POPIA does indeed apply to health research: A response to Bronstein and Nyachowe. *S Afr Med J* 2023;113(11):e1394. <https://doi.org/10.7196/SAMJ.2023.v113i11.1394>

³ Bronstein V, Nyachowe DT. Building coherence in the regulation of health research: A reply to Thaldar. *S Afr Med J* 2023;113(11):e1394. <https://doi.org/10.7196/SAMJ.2023.v113i11.1394>

In 2022, Brand et al. published an article in the *South African Journal of Science* on data sharing governance in sub-Saharan Africa during public health emergencies.⁴ Their article contained various legal inaccuracies. To clarify these issues, we published a response article.⁵ The academic dialogue could have concluded following our initial response. However, Brand et al. chose to issue a rebuttal, accusing us of misinterpreting their work.⁶ This charge necessitates a thorough rejoinder. In our current response, we not only reaffirm the accuracy of our interpretation of Brand et al.’s original article, but also identify a significant new legal error in their subsequent rebuttal. Furthermore, we delve deeper into the fundamental lapses in rigour evident in Brand et al.’s approach. In conclusion, given the cumulative shortcomings in adherence to the foundational principles of rigour in legal research, we contend that both articles by Brand et al. are deficient and recommend their retraction.

Analysis

Ghana

Brand et al. initially characterise Ghana’s data protection legislation as inadequate for protecting data subjects regarding the export of personal data, stating it “does not contain any provisions pertaining to cross-border transfer of personal information”. We counter this assertion, clarifying that the Ghanaian *Data Protection Act* 843 of 2012 (DPA) encompasses all transfers of personal data—both domestic *and international* (section 96). In essence, the Ghanaian DPA does not differentiate between domestic and international data transfers. Moreover, the Ghanaian DPA extends its jurisdiction to include foreign data processors (section 30(4)). The flaw in Brand et al.’s argument lies in their assumption that the lack of explicit provisions on international data transfers in the Ghanaian DPA implies an absence of legal regulation of such transfers.

We further highlight that the Ghanaian DPA provides for an extra layer of protection for sensitive data, which includes health data; and that sensitive data may only be transferred—within or outside of Ghana—if there is consent, or the transfer is necessary for medical purposes, which are defined to include health research (section 37(6) and (7) of the Ghanaian DPA). In their rebuttal, Brand et al. fail to engage with these important points. Instead, they focus on how the Ghanaian DPA deals with the personal data of foreign data subjects in Ghana. This is followed by the non-sequitur that the Ghanaian DPA “compares unfavourably” with other countries’ data protection legislation and offers “inadequate protection” to Ghanaian data subjects in relation to data transfers to foreign jurisdictions.

⁴ Brand D, Singh JA, Nienaber McKay AG, Cengiz N, Moodley K. Data sharing governance in sub-Saharan Africa during public health emergencies: Gaps and guidance. *S Afr J Sci.* 2022;118(11/12), Art. #13892. <https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2022/13892>

⁵ Thaldar D, Abdulrauf L, Ogendi P, Gooden A, Donnelly D-L, Townsend B. Response to Brand et al. (2022) Data sharing governance in sub-Saharan Africa during public health emergencies. *S Afr J Sci.* 2023;119(11/12), Art. #15722. <https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2023/15722>

⁶ Brand D, Singh JA, Nienaber McKay AG, Cengiz N, Moodley K. A response to Thaldar et al. (2023): Data sharing governance in sub-Saharan Africa during public health emergencies. *S Afr J Sci.* 2023;119(11/12), Art. #16896. <https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2023/16896>

Kenya

In their original article, Brand et al. characterise Kenya’s data protection legislation as “strict”. This assessment is based on a definition of “strict” that the authors devise themselves, without any substantiation, and which reads as follows: “Countries with stringent rules require notification of, or approval by, a relevant data protection authority, and/or special conditions (such as proof of appropriate safeguards with respect to the protection and security of personal data), as well as consent from the data subject.” Even though Brand et al.’s article is focused on public health emergencies, Brand et al. fail to recognise the public health emergency exception in Kenyan law (*Data Protection (General) Regulations, 2021 (DPGR)*, regulations 55–57). When this exception is triggered by a public health emergency, *no* notification, approval, or consent is required for cross-border transfer. Hence, in the context of Brand et al.’s article—public health emergencies—Kenyan law is (according to Brand et al.’s own definition) *not* strict.

In our response, we point out Brand et al.’s failure to recognise and consider this most relevant legal provision in Kenyan law in the context of public health emergencies. Additionally, it is noteworthy that the authors failed to discuss or even mention the Kenyan DPGR in their original article—despite its relevance as a primary source of Kenyan data protection law. In their rebuttal, Brand et al. acknowledge that the public health emergencies exception is indeed part of Kenyan law. However, they attempt to downplay its importance by asserting that the public health emergency exception is a “very specific” exception to the general rule, and that their categorisation of Kenyan law as strict relate to the “overall approach” taken in Kenya. By contrast, the titles of both their original article and rebuttal article make it clear that they position their study in the “very specific” context of public health emergencies. Moreover, in their original article they explicitly delineate their study as follows: “We explore governance considerations that ought to apply to the collection, transfer, and use of data in *public health emergencies*”. [Emphasis added.] To claim in their rebuttal that their “strict” categorisation of Kenyan law relate to some “overall approach” is disingenuous.

Nigeria

Regulation 2.11 of the *Nigeria Data Protection Regulation, 2019 (NDPR)* provides that the Attorney General and National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) are responsible for making adequacy decisions, i.e., decide which countries provide adequate data protection. The implications of these adequacy decisions are twofold: First, data transfers to countries assessed as adequate are treated akin to domestic transfers. Second, transfers to countries without such adequacy must satisfy certain conditions, such as obtaining data subject consent to the transfer and being in the public interest, as outlined in regulation 2.12 of the NDPR. However, in their original article, Brand et al. seem to refer to these adequacy decisions as *authorisation* by the relevant entities. In our response, we highlight that this is problematic, as adequacy decisions and authorisation are two distinct concepts. To elaborate: The concept *authorisation* by relevant state authorities in the data protection context typically refers to the process whereby data providers apply for approval from such authorities for specific (individual or kinds of) data transfer transactions. (E.g., sections 27(2) and 35(2) of POPIA.) By contrast, adequacy decisions do not require application by data providers, nor relate to specific data transfer transactions. Rather, adequacy decisions are general in nature and may entail engagement between state authorities and their counterparts in other countries.

However, in their rebuttal, Brand et al. simply assert—without proffering reasons or citing authority—that adequacy decisions effectively equate to authorisation. They state:

“Authorisation for international data transfer was provided by way of a [adequacy] decision by NITDA.” We suggest that clarity is better served by not conflating adequacy decisions with authorisation.

In their rebuttal, Brand et al. also assert—without providing any references or reasons—that the new *Nigerian Data Protection Act, 2023* (NDPA), has *repealed* the NDPR. This assertion is incorrect. In fact, section 64(2)(f) of the NDPA preserves the NDPR.

South Africa

In their original article, Brand et al. fail to recognise that South African law currently requires, amongst others, prior authorisation from the Information Regulator for cross-border transfers of health data (section 57 of POPIA). This is a major and highly consequential omission that we highlight in our response. It is relevant to note that this omission is in Table 1 of the authors’ article that lists legal requirements of various countries for cross-border transfer of personal data. When referring to Table 1 in the text of their article, the authors cite as their reference not any primary source, but an online report published by the Alliance for E-Trade Development.⁷ The report gives no indication that it was peer-reviewed or subject to any other quality control mechanism. The report contains its own table of countries and, *inter alia*, those countries’ purported legal requirements for cross-border data transfer. Conspicuously, it omits prior authorisation in the case of South Africa. This illustrates the pitfalls of relying on non-peer-reviewed online documents.

In our response, we further note that the requirement for prior authorisation will fall away if and when a code of conduct is approved for the research sector. In their rebuttal, Brand et al. appear to concur with this view. However, there is disagreement on the topic of the proposed Code of Conduct for Research that was developed by the Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf) and that is currently under consideration by the Information Regulator. In their original article, Brand et al.’s language clearly suggest that they view the proposed Code as presently binding. For example, they state that “The Code is intended to provide guidance to the research community about the use of data in research *and is binding.*” [Emphasis added.] In our response, we point out that the proposed Code is still pending approval, possibly subject to amendments, and thus, not yet binding. In their rebuttal, Brand et al. assert, rather tersely, that they refer to the (proposed) Code of Conduct for Research as “the Code” because ASSAf does so. This deflection from the issue of the proposed Code’s binding nature is unconvincing. As reference for their assertion, the authors cite the (proposed) Code of Conduct for Research as published on ASSAf’s website.⁸ Notably, on page three this document states—in yellow highlight—that “This Code will come into effect on [insert date once agreed with the Information Regulator]” (original text in square brackets, paragraph B.3.3). This explicit reference to a future activation date, pending agreement with the Information Regulator, unequivocally indicates the document’s draft status. Did the authors not read their own reference?

⁷ Suominen K, Vambell E. Alliance for E-Trade Development: Toward an African data transfer regime to enable MSMEs’ cross-border ecommerce [document on the Internet]. c2021 [cited 3 Dec 2023]. Available from: https://www.allianceforetradedevelopment.org/_files/ugd/478c1a_72021e35a826441db0723642a79e65e5.pdf

⁸ Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf). POPIA Code of Conduct for Research [document on the Internet]. c2023 [cited 3 Dec 2023]. Available from: <https://www.assaf.org.za/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/ASSAf-POPIACode-of-Conduct-for-Research.pdf>

Furthermore, to dispel any residual doubt, one can resort to an authoritative source: the *Gazette*. Section 62 of POPIA provides that all codes of conduct that are approved by the Information Regulator must be published in the *Gazette*. A search of the *Gazette* reveals that the proposed Code, while published for public comment in terms of section 61 of POPIA,⁹ has not yet been published as an approved code of conduct by the Information Regulator. Accordingly, the (proposed) Code of Conduct for Research is *not* legally binding.

In light of these findings, it is perplexing that Brand et al. opt to levy an unsubstantiated accusation of misinterpretation against us, rather than conceding an apparent error in their initial analysis. The evidence unambiguously shows that the proposed Code, in its present iteration, is not legally binding. Such acknowledgment of an error, though perhaps uncomfortable, is pivotal in maintaining scholarly integrity and fostering constructive dialogue in the academic community.

Conclusion

Brand et al.'s original article and subsequent rebuttal exhibit a departure from the standards of rigour in legal research. Their reliance on a secondary, non-peer-reviewed internet source, and neglect of primary legal texts, led to inaccuracies and misinterpretations of data protection laws across various African countries. Our responses have been consistently directed towards rectifying these inaccuracies. Significantly, Brand et al.'s rebuttal lacks any evidence or examples to substantiate their allegation that we misinterpreted their work. Their defence, marked by logical disconnects and deflection, only serves to further highlight the lapses in their adherence to rigour. Given these circumstances, the most appropriate course of action for Brand et al. would be to retract both their initial publication and their ensuing rebuttal.

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⁹ Information Regulator [South Africa] (2023) Notice in terms of section 61(2) of the Protection of Personal Information Act no 4 of 2013 (POPIA) code of conduct: The Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf). *Government Gazette* no 48589 of 12 May 2023. Available from: <https://inforegulator.org.za/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Government-Gazette-dated-12-May-.pdf>